

Identifying the Effective Factors on Participation in Public Sports in West Azerbaijan Province

Received: 2020-11-14

Accepted: 2020-12-19

Vol. 2, No.3. Summer. 2021, 37-50

Somayeh Alizadeh¹
Hamid Janani^{2*}
Mohamad Rahim Najafzadeh²
Jafar barghi Moghadam²
Amir Dana³

¹Ph.D. Student of Sport Management, Islamic Azad University, Tabriz Branch, Tabriz, Iran

²Assistant Professor of Physical Education, Islamic Azad University, Tabriz Branch, Tabriz, Iran

³Assistant Professor of Physical Education, Islamic Azad University, Gonbad Kavous Branch, Gonbad Kavous, Iran

*Correspondence:
Hamid Janani, Assistant Professor of Physical Education, Islamic Azad University, Tabriz Branch, Tabriz, Iran

Email: janani@iaut.ac.ir
Orcid: [0000-0002-6464-0790](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6464-0790)

Abstract

Purpose: Despite the positive approaches of the management of the sports system and the health system in public leisure, there are still numerous reports and documented shreds of evidence of mobility poverty and its consequences in the urban life of people in deprived provinces, which indicates a worrying social problem. **Methods:** Therefore, the researcher conducted this study by identifying the factors affecting participation in sports by using a grounded theory approach. The statistical population of the study included the elites of physical education and the sampling of the participants was done theoretically and purposefully. The data collection tool was a semi-structured interview and the data obtained from the interviews were analyzed using a Strauss and Corbin coding approach method.

Results: In the results of code grouping, 39 components were obtained in five areas of causal, contextual, interventional, strategy, and consequence factors.

Conclusion: Based on the research findings, it can be said that the popularization of sports in West Azerbaijan province can be achieved through the support of environmental factors, the positive intervention of managerial factors, resource contextualization, and finally, through behavioral factors. Therefore, it is necessary that the effective policies on sports participation in this province be identified and analyzed based on the model.

Keywords: Sports Participation, Public Sports, West Azerbaijan Province.

Introduction

One of the most important consequences of activity in society is the occurrence of stress and psychological pressures (Khajavi & Khan Mohammadi, 2015). Life in today's world has taken the quick initiative from man and has left him with mobility poverty, which has caused him many physical, psychological, and social problems (Neuparth, 2014). With the significant increase in the role of sports in the economic, social, cultural, and even political development of countries, progress in the field of sports has become one of the strategic priorities of planners in different countries of the world (Ali Doust Ghahfarkhi et al, 2014) to the extent that sports as an exciting and motivating phenomenon, creator of national unity, the factor of development and promotion of health in society, has taken an important place in the societies (McChesney, 1989). Meanwhile, the need to develop sports has led to its expansion in different societies; in the meantime, lack of justice in programs, manpower, and equipment related to sports has led to the formation of sports poverty (De Grace et al, 2017). The deep gap between the viewpoints and the practice of the non-application of physical education knowledge shows that the available facilities and resources have not been used properly (Webb, 2016). On the other hand, the Center for Strategic Studies of Iran in its report showed that the participation of men and women in public sports programs in 2015 compared to 2013 has decreased by 13% and 0.03%, respectively (Fathi et al, 2018). Also, the director of the Public Sports Development Center of Iran announced in an interview that 56% of the people are inactive. This decrease in mobility and physical activity in daily life, which is caused by the development and expansion of facilities and amenities and new ways of life, highlights the need for planning for physical activities needed by the society (Hosseini et al, 2017).

Given these circumstances, the most important necessity and duty of sports policymakers is to pay attention to the spread of sports among the general public by planning different models of public sports growth in the future, but the problem is that these models can be different in the future. Therefore, any change in the future must be preceded by planned, long-term and patient changes in the culture of society (Taheri Demneh, 2015). In recent years, various institutions in the field of physical education and sports have designed and implemented several programs; however, due to the lack of sufficient coordination and coherence, they did not have the required efficiency and it seems that this failure still continues after the development of a comprehensive sports plan (Ranjbari et al, 2018). In many societies, people face problems and inequalities such as lack of access to educational facilities, poverty, and unequal income in society, to which physical education and sports can be added (Toro, 2005). According to the previous research, exercise, and physical activity increase self-confidence, avoidance of drugs, lack of sexual dysfunction, academic achievement, and they reduce crime in society (Dollman & Lewis, 2010). But there are many problems in sports and participation in it because this includes a lack of facilities, equipment, sports fields, and cultural misconceptions in society (Ehsani et al, 2009). Meanwhile, researchers investigated the individual consequences of participating in sports, such as general health, mental health, and quality of life. At the organizational and managerial level, researchers such as Sajjadi et al (2018) probed the management of the Sports Development Center at the Ministry of Sports and Youth. Seyed Ameri & Mohammad Alaq (2012) proposed solutions for the development of public sports, focused on the effectiveness of programs of this type of sports. Generally, most of the organizational

level research were conducted on municipal sports (Hosseini et al, 2018; Nejad Sajjadi et al, 2016) and university sports (Manafi et al, 2015) and in some cases, they were done on various military organizations. However, in macro and strategic studies, Mozaffari & Qarah (2005) compared public sports in Iran and several selected countries, and also Khaki et al (2005) investigated the experts' views on the development of this sport (Nowruzi, 2018). A lot of scientific and empirical evidence has been found on the known benefits of physical activity and sports participation; however, national reports still show a high percentage of sports poverty among members of society (Shahbazi et al, 2013). The development of sports and the reduction of mobility poverty in people is one of the most sustainable ways to prevent corruption, deviations, and behavioral disorders, which leads to having a better environment and social life (Spansol, 2019). Accordingly, the need to identify the factors affecting the existence of sports poverty among individuals is strongly felt because based on available statistics, Iran and its provinces do not have a good place in the world rankings in the development of sports (Banar et al, 2016). The results of studies conducted in this field have also shown the occurrence of the issue. Ranjbari et al (2018) Some obstacles to participation in sports activities such as families not paying attention to sports in deprived and poor areas of the country, the existence of natural and geographical changes in some deprived areas and creating some natural problems in these areas, lack of training programs in sports in deprived and poor areas, weakness Farhangi announced the use of all classes and groups present in deprived and impoverished areas. Sajjadi et al (2015) Bureaucratic structure, ambiguity in tasks, interference of tasks and dispersion were reported as factors of incoherence and integration in the structure of Iranian sports. Banar et al (2016) reported

that participation management factors, participation services, development resources, environmental context, sports capabilities, and individual background, respectively, have a significant effect on the level of sports participation (as the dependent variable). Clutterbuck and Doherty (2019) concluded that for sports development, the emphasis should be on strategic planning along with sustainable investment, facilities, financial aid, familiarity with development issues, helping others, and helping sport itself. Bell (2003) reported that the hypothesis of '*positive economy*' and '*heritage*' in sports participation also depends on the equitable distribution of scarce resources, especially in disadvantaged communities. Impacts on those who participate in sports or the development of individuals through sport may also be described as "soft heritage". Avgerinou (2017) showed that the development of sports in various dimensions such as participation, marketing, leisure, culture, etc. can lead to national development and peace. In examining the role of sport in sustainable development. De Grace et al (2017) reported that the functions of sport play a significant role in health indicators and social participation. The problem of low indicators of health and social vitality and lack of activity and mobility among members of society are among the important challenges of the country. This problem has always been the concern of government officials and social experts, and also, they were the pillars of the macro-socio-cultural policy of the country and social criticism. The main area in creating a healthy and vibrant society is to pay attention to an active lifestyle and rich leisure time. In fact, numerous studies have shown the beneficial and lasting physical and psychological effects of sport in different classes of society. The importance and necessity of physical activities and recreational sports in maintaining and

promoting the physical and mental health of individuals and society is clear and special attention should be paid to the expansion of sports at the community level, which is one of the priorities of governments. The most basic way that helps to achieve this issue is to study the factors influencing the attraction of people to this category, which should be done based on specialized studies. Therefore, according to the mentioned cases and according to the functions of sports in society, it is necessary to identify the factors affecting sports poverty among the people of society through scientific study in this field. Because the effort to remove these obstacles requires sufficient scientific evidence in this area. In order to plan sports in the community properly, the study of the causes of sports poverty is considered as one of the possible solutions in this field. According to the mentioned cases, the researcher in this study seeks to find an answer to the question: 'What is the pattern of factors affecting sports poverty in West Azerbaijan province?'

Materials and Methods

This research is an applied study that has been conducted qualitatively and in the form of grounded theory (derived from data) and it has been done based on the approach of research projects by which a theory is developed using a set of data. The participation of this study includes all experts in sports (female sports managers; professional athletes; university professors and experts who have written or have articles in this field) who were selected using the snowball method (chain reference). In this study, according to the purpose of the research, purposive sampling method was performed theoretically and based on snowball method with a focus on theory development. The participants took part in a semi-structured interview. In this regard, questions were designed as an interview guide and three interviews were run in the pilot study, and afterward, the questions were

modified. Reliability and generalizability (verifiability) are considered as measures of the validity of qualitative research. The term validity is commensurate with internal validity; the ability to generalize to external validity; and reliability has been defined as stability of the results. The retest method and intra-subject reliability were used to evaluate the coding reliability of the interviews. To calculate the retest, three interviews were selected from the interviews and each of them was re-coded by the researcher of the present study at a short and specific time interval. The identified codes were then compared at two-time intervals for each interview. The results of this coding are shown in Table 1. The reliability of the retest for the interviews of this study using the mentioned formula was equal to 0.84%. Given that this reliability rate is more than 56%, the reliability of the coding is confirmed and it can be claimed that the reliability of the interview analysis was appropriate.

To calculate the reliability of the interview with the method of two coders' intra-subject agreement, a Ph.D. student in sports management, who had more than 10 years of experience in the field of public sports, was asked to participate in the coding as a colleague. Then, the researcher and her colleague coded three interviews and obtained the percentage of intra-subject agreement using the following formula:

$$(\text{Number of agreement} \times 2) / (\text{number of codes}) \times 100 = \text{percentage of intra-subject agreement}$$

The reliability of the retest for the interviews in this study using the mentioned formula was equal to 77%. Given that the reliability rate is more than 60%, the reliability of the coding was confirmed and it can be claimed that the reliability of the interviews was appropriate. Data analysis was also performed based on the grounded approach. The specific objectives of this study included

identifying common structures, categories, and concepts to explain the conceptual model. The analysis was performed in three stages of open, axial, and selective coding.

In this section, the characteristics of research samples have been reported in the form of position, field of study, education, and field of activity.

Results

Table 1. Demographic characteristics of research participants

Row	Position	Education	Field of Study	Field of Activity	
				Faculty member	Executive
1	Head of Welfare Department of Urmia Municipality	MA	Law and Jurisprudence	-	*
2	Director of Physical Education in Urmia	MA	Management	-	*
3	Head of Sports and Youth Department of Urmia	Ph.D.	Sports Management	-	*
4	Director of the Sports Organization of West Azerbaijan Province	Ph.D.	Sports Management	*	*
5	Faculty member	Ph.D.	Sports Management	*	-
6	The person in charge of the physical education department of the West Azerbaijan Sports Organization	MA	Sport physiology	-	*
7	Expert of Deputy Planning of Urmia Municipality	Ph.D. candidate	Sports Management	*	*
8	Deputy Director of Sports of the General Directorate of Sports and Youth	MA	Sports Management	*	*
9	Deputy Director of Physical Education of the Education Department	MA	Sports Management	-	*
10	Head of Urmia Ghahremani Base	Ph.D. candidate	Sports Management	-	*
11	Expert in charge of physical education of the Education Department	MA	Sports Management	*	*
12	Head of the physical education department of the Province	Ph.D. candidate	Sport physiology	-	*
13	Secretary of the Public Sports Board of the Province	Ph.D.	Management	-	*
14	Deputy of Sports Management of Urmia Municipality	Ph.D. candidate	Management	-	*
15	Head of Miandoab Youth and Sports Department	BA	Sports Management	-	*
16	The Person in Charge of sports affairs of Urmia Municipality	Ph.D. candidate	Sports Management	-	*
17	Faculty member at Urmia University	Ph.D.	Sports Management	-	*
18	Faculty member at Islamic Azad University of Urmia	Ph.D.	Sports Management	*	*
19	Faculty member at Islamic Azad University of Urmia	Ph.D.	Sports Management	-	*
20	Faculty member at Islamic Azad University of Urmia	Ph.D.	Pathology	*	*

Table 2. Sample Text of the Interview

People in West Azerbaijan province are not satisfied with small scale sports programs, and the main and most important part that has been missed is to motivate citizens. Citizens must be introduced to the benefits of sports through science, recreation, and entertainment programs. In schools, universities, etc., we do not pay for sports in cities, we pay for not dying. Some people do not care about exercising at all and they do not see exercise as one of their necessities and needs. We need to build the intellectual infrastructure, and if that happens, people will pay the expenses.

An example of open-ended coding and an interview that has been done with the interviewees has been provided in Table 2.

Now that all the data has been encoded and several initial codes or concepts have been created, the second stage of open coding begins. The researcher at this stage has nothing to do with raw texts, rather, she deals with the concepts she has produced. The purpose of this stage of open coding, also known as "centralized" coding, is to generate and extract major categories. Categories are concepts of a higher level of abstraction and allow the analyst to reduce and integrate data (Mohammadpour, 2013). After coding the first level, 346 codes were obtained. Then in the second level of coding to 37 central codes.

The second step of data coding is known as axial encoding. At this stage, the categories are connected as a network. As can be seen, while performing the analysis, the researcher obtained several basic codes. The important point here is that these codes must be basic, that is, similar phenomena must be classified, otherwise we get caught up in so many concepts that we do not know what to do with them. Once we have identified a particular phenomenon in the data, then we can group the concepts around them. This reduces the number of units we have to work with. The process of classifying concepts that seem to be related to similar phenomena is called categorization. Then we give a conceptual name to the category that includes the phenomenon. It should be noted that this name should be more abstract than conceptual names (Charms, 60-57).

Table3. Open and axial coding (centralized)

Axial Coding	Central Code/Secondary	Indicator
Psychological	Motivational	P3, P16, P6, P2, P11, P1
Facilities and equipment	Providing the necessary infrastructure	, P3, P2, P20, P18, P17, P16, P13, P1 P5, P14, P19, P10, P9, P8, P7, P6
	Access	P7, P3
	Active Transportation	P19, P7, P5, P3
Capacity	Disseminators of citizenship sports	, P13, P12, P11, P16, P17, P19, P9 P6, P20, P7, P6, P3, P2, P1, P15, P14
	Using existing capacities	P18, P17, P15, P14, P12
Sustainable Development	Laying the groundwork for progress	P7
Progress in health	Maintaining Health	P4, P2
	Increasing vitality and improving mood	P2, P18, P19, P7
Institutionalization	Increasing participation	P15, P19, P16, P14, P2, P17
Attraction	Sports attractions	P6, P8, P7
	Environmental attractions	P19, P9, P20, P13
Behavioral	Understanding sports	P10, P7, P20, P2
	Changing attitude	P8, P6, P19
Culture	Information	P20, P10, P13, P6
	Awareness	, P8, P7, P5, P6, P1, P20, P9, P3, P2 P19
Policy making	Competence	, P10, P4, P2, P12, P13, P8, P16, P11 P7, P5
	Coordination	P4, P16, P5, P2
	Integration	P12, P11, P13, P19
	Sectioning	P6, P17, P10, P11
Financial and human capital	Financial Support	P12, P2, P19
	Managerial	P10, P3, P9, P1
Study and needs analysis	Needs analysis	P11, P7, P19, P1, P10, P6
	earning knowledge	P11, P10, P1
obstacles	Structural	, P19, P1, P10, P13, P12, P7, P3, P2 P9, P14, P6, P16
	Knowledge	P20, P18, P13
	Specifying the program and strategy	P17, P16, P18
	Financial	P16, P15, P5, P1
	Cognitive	P19, P10, P17, P12, P9, P7, P1
	Legal	P11, P10
	Infrastructure	P5, P18, P17
	Individual	P10, P11
	Informational	P7
Human	P19, P10, P7	
Macro	Strategy: Level 1	, P9, P13, P10, P3, P8, P6, P5, P4 P2, P20, P17, P19
Executive	Strategy: Level 3	, P15, P14, P5, P13, P9, P17, P4, P2 P11, P13, P7, P6, P18
Middle	Strategy: Level 2	, P5, P20, P8, P7, P13, P10, P9, P2 P3, P4, P15, P8, P1

As shown above, the researcher examined the factors affecting participation in public sports in West Azerbaijan province. According to the results, 16 factors were identified as the final codes, which finally 5 core categories were extracted.

At this stage, the researcher adjusted the main phenomena to achieve the desired integration, which ultimately resulted in the obtained theorization for participation in

public sports. The results obtained from Table 3 allow individuals to use this data to predict the factors affecting sports participation in West Azerbaijan Province. The categories obtained in this table are all based on the quantitative and empirical attitudes of the interviewees. In this section, combined axial coding was performed and the content of each of them was placed in the form of theoretical codes.

Table 4. Theoretical coding (selective)

Theoretical coding	Axial coding	Indicator
Causal factors	Psychological	P3, P16, P6, P2, P11, P1
contextual factors	Facilities and equipment	, P9, P8, P7, P6, P3, P2, P20, P18, P17, P16, P13, P1 P5, P14, P19, P10
contextual factors	Capacity	, P2, P1, P15, P14, P13, P12, P11, P16, P17, P19, P9 , P18, P6, P20, P7, P6, P3
consequences	Sustainable Development	P7, P4, P2, P15, P19, P16, P14, P2, P17
	Progress in health	
	Institutionalization	
Interventional factors	Attraction	P19, P9, P20, P13, P6, P8, P7
Interventional factors	Behavioral	P8, P6, P19, P10, P7, P20, P2
Intervening factors	Policy making and planning	, P20, P19, P7, P5, P10, P4, P2, P12, P13, P8, P16, P11 P6, P17
Causal factors	Financial and human capital	P10, P3, P9, P1, P12, P2, P19
Causal factors	Study and needs analysis	P11, P7, P19, P1, P10, P6
contextual factors	Obstacles	, P9, P14, P6, P16, P19, P1, P10, P13, P12, P7, P3, P2 , P8, P1, P15, P5, P20, P18
Macro	Strategy: Level 1	P2, P20, P17, P19, P9, P13, P10, P3, P8, P6, P5, P4
Executive	Strategy: Level 3	, P13, P7, P6, P18, P15, P14, P5, P13, P9, P17, P4, P2 P11
Middle	Strategy: Level 2	P3, P4, P15, P8, P1, P5, P20, P8, P7, P13, P10, P9, P2

Fig 1. The final model of Participation in Public Sports in West Azerbaijan Province

Discussion

The results showed that the main indicators of causal conditions affecting sports poverty in West Azerbaijan province in this study include the categories of study and needs analysis, psychology, and financial and human capital. Needs analysis has long been considered as one of the main axes in the areas that deal with planning and forecasting goals; and needs analysis that provides social, cultural, and health services, especially in sports, has a special place. Awareness of the need is used as the main criterion for providing various services and implementing various sports programs in the province, the proper use of which can reduce sports poverty among people in a community. As the study of sports needs category shows, countries that have succeeded in popularizing sports in order to reduce physical poverty and increase healthy

recreation based on physical activity among their citizens, have based the process of providing their sports services based on the needs announced by the people. Another category related to the causal factors related to sports poverty in West Azerbaijan Province is the psychological category. This factor indicates the role of psychological factors in sports poverty. One of the psychological axes that is important in the discussion of people's participation in public sports is the motivational factor. Considering the situation of mobility poverty in the study population, the role of psychological and motivational factors is very important and significant. Therefore, societies that improve the psychological ability of people in society along with increasing technical efficiency can reduce mobility poverty, which subsequently leads to achieving significant success in making societies healthier.

Psychological terms such as tastes, needs, wants, incentives etc. have been used to describe the factors that cause mobility in people. At the same time, factors such as anxiety, stress, and various psychological states have particular impacts on human actions. Obviously, the psychological factors involved in sports poverty are extremely complex. The results of this question showed that the category of financial and human capital is one of the causal factors affecting sports poverty in West Azerbaijan province. Another result of this study was that the contextual indicators in this study include the categories of facilities and equipment, capacity, and barriers. Having sports facilities and equipment is a citizen's right all over the world. In this study, lack of policy-making, lack of principled care, and lack of accurate and codified planning, and lack of strategic plans regarding equipment and facilities are the most important factors in the occurrence of sports poverty in Azerbaijan province. The most important factors identified in sports facilities and equipment include the provision of infrastructure, access, and transportation. Providing sports infrastructure will increase sports participation and reduce mobility in the community. Several studies have emphasized that the existence of sports infrastructure will have a positive effect on reducing mobility poverty in a society (Lim et al, 2011). Therefore, it is very important to know how many and what sports facilities are available near the residents' homes. The mental perception of the existence of sports facilities is often different from the actual existence. It is important to consider the real existence objectively. In the meantime, proximity and access are among the most important issues in doing physical activity and reducing sports poverty among citizens. One of the most important problems in the cities of the province, and especially in the center of our province, is the inappropriate placement of

sports complexes among other urban uses so that many people in the community cannot have a desired use from sports venues due to lack of access to them. The distribution of sports facilities in the city and its different areas has a direct effect on the desired model and functional efficiency of the city, so that many people, especially certain groups (such as the elderly and women) mentioned that lack of access to these facilities is the main reason for their mobility poverty. To solve this problem, all city agencies must use the necessary coordination. The most important thing to note here is the difference between public sports and public sports. The most common international term for public sports is "Sports for all". Public sport is a sport that all people everywhere and whenever they can, in any field they want to play, whether individually or in groups do it to promote vitality, freshness, and health of body and soul (Salimi, 2011). Accordingly, the category of capacity, including the development and dissemination of citizenship sports can be considered as the most important factor in public participation and reducing poverty in sports and physical activity.

On the other hand, the indicators of intervention conditions in this research include the categories of policy-making and planning, attractiveness, and morality. The policy-making system in Iran has special epistemological and theoretical foundations that create appropriate tools and techniques; therefore, in order to understand politics and policy-making, knowing these foundations, on the one hand, helps to optimize future policy-making processes and, on the other hand, acquaints us with existing strengths, weaknesses, and the existing gaps. Meanwhile, the province's sports planners offer different answers to the general sports challenges depending on the economic, cultural, and political conditions. Due to the low proportion of physical activists in the

country, sports poverty in West Azerbaijan Province can be considered recognized as a public problem, a need, shortage, limitation, or a significant dissatisfaction in society. Accordingly, the country's sports policy should be formulated in such a way that also economic, political, and legal components, citizens are associated with these policies and they should be based on ethics, and a regular system of physical and movement activity should be formulated based on the values that govern society. Another case in point is the attractiveness of the environment and the attractiveness of the nature of sports. The growth and promotion of physical activity requires the identification of the factors that affect it, which includes a wide range of sectors. Since sports settings play an important role in this field, more attention should be paid to their productivity and steps should be taken to improve it.

Obviously, the larger the location, the greater the number of access routes to create more options for people to travel. On the other hand, the many traffic routes are valuable if each one is easily recognizable because if they are not designed properly, the multiplicity of ways will confuse people. The short distance between different sports venues is another factor that is less important to the participants than the previous two. Due to the large size of this complex and enough space for parking lots, most of the customers of the complex come to the complex by their vehicles. In such cases, the distance between the places does not matter much. Indicators of sports poverty strategies in West Azerbaijan province in this study include macro, medium, and micro strategies. Explaining this finding, it can be said that people's sports participation is affected by micro-level factors, which include: income, level of education, parental education, and such factors. It is worth noting that personal income has been mentioned as one of the important indicators in the rate of sports

poverty; in a way that, in order to perform many sports, it will be necessary to provide equipment suitable for that sport (Hsu et al, 2010). The components of human capital also determine the level of participation in sports. In recent research, the level of personal education has been pointed out and it has been shown that people with higher levels of education turn to more diverse sports and learn more motor skills. In addition, it is important to educated people are more aware of the positive effects of participating in sports on human health. Social values in sports participation can be different between men and women. Most previous studies have shown that men are more interested in participating in sports than women (Ruski & Humphreys, 2011). In addition, gender-specific differences, depending on the value of sport, depend in particular on the person's cultural background. As a result, culture can limit participation in sports.

Conclusion

Finally, outcome indicators in this study include the categories of sustainable development, progress in health, and institutionalization. Explaining this finding, it can be said that a healthy human being, a healthy society, and a healthy life are the goals of sustainable development. Social problems and anomalies are among the most important and fundamental issues of our society today. The economic, social, political, and security consequences of social problems are enormous. The not-so-beautiful statistics of our society show this bitter reality. One of the most sustainable ways to prevent corruption, deviations, and behavioral abnormalities, and to improve the environment and social life is to develop and popularize sports. The development of sports and physical education, as a basic measure to provide and train healthy human capital, is a national duty. The generalization of sports is the basis of making people and the

community healthy. It should be noted that it is the performance of a healthy person that provides a healthy life and a healthy society. The model of human performance consists of three elements: environment, activity, and people. People and their general conditions are the most complex elements in the model of performance. Now we have to see what characteristics a person should have in order to organize regular physical activity and to adapt and use the environment, life, and sustainable development. If we refer to our overall culture, we find significant and interesting categories that have been raised in the past but have not been institutionalized, such as a healthy mind in a healthy body. If we believed that a healthy mind is in a healthy body, and a wise person is the main element of social activities, what healthy bodies with healthy minds could we train with 12 years of education until graduation and 16 years until bachelor's degree? Neither the sports teacher nor the sports score found a place in the education and health of the workforce. Nowadays, with the formation of non-profit and non-governmental schools, despite the enormous increase in tuition fees, there is no space for sports and physical education, and most residential houses have been turned into schools that do not have suitable space for breathing and physical activity. At the same time, our society has caught itself to the extent that the opportunity for any real fun and joy and happiness has been taken away. In other words, our people today are so immersed in themselves that the only thing they do not think about is the health of their bodies, souls, and having adequate joy and happiness. Exercise and physical education is an uplifting category for the public. The latent forces will be evacuated from the youth in a proper way and it is an inevitable necessity for the middle-aged and the elderly people. Municipalities and the physical education organizations are obliged to provide suitable, cheap, free, and

accessible environments for people's sports according to their legal duties. It remains to be seen how the necessary resources for these facilities will be provided. The third and fourth development plans have authorized all government agencies to spend at least one percent of their total budget, including current, civil, and private, on the expansion of spaces and the development of sports. Half of this amount this year equals one thousand billion tomans. If the officials of the executive apparatus consider common sense in the healthy body as the main factor of productivity and development, using this authority will create a revolution in physical education and the youth will be prevented from all kinds of social corruption. It tolerates drug use and what families whose youth are not caught in the trap of addiction and all kinds of deviations and what youth who do not get lost and how effective this heavy cost is.

References

1. AliDust Ghahfarkh, I., Sajjadi, S. N., Mahmoudi, A., & Saat Chian, V. (2014). Investigating the priorities and strategies for the development of the sport of national judo championship. *Sports Management*, 6(2), 246-231.
2. Aman, M. S., Mohamed, M., & Omar-Fauzee, M. S. (2009). Sport for all and elite sport: underlining values and aims for government involvement via leisure policy. *European journal of social sciences*, 9(4), 659-668.
3. Avgerinou, V., Skoula, E., Papaioannou, A., & Kriemadis, T. (2017). Strategic planning in the sport sector. *Choregia: Sport Management International Journal*, 13(2), 35-52.
4. Bell, W. (2003). *Foundations of Futures Studies: History, Purposes and Knowledge: Human Science for a New Era*, Vol. 1. New Brunswick and London: Transaction Publishers.

5. Clutterbuck, R., & Doherty, A. (2019). Organizational capacity for domestic sport for development. *Journal of Sport for Development*, 7(12), 16-32.
6. de Grace, L. A., Knight, C. J., Rodgers, W. M., & Clark, A. M. (2017). Exploring the role of sport in the development of substance addiction. *Psychology of Sport and Exercise*, 28, 46-57.
7. Dollman, J., & Lewis, N. R. (2010). The impact of socioeconomic position on sport participation among South Australian youth. *Journal of Science and Medicine in Sport*, 13(3), 318-322.
8. Ehsani, M., Shetab Bushehri, N., & Koozechian, H. (2009). Investigating and ranking of factors preventing the promotion of women to managerial positions in sports delegations of Khuzestan province. *Research in Sports Science*, 19(5), 171-190.
9. Fathi, F., Sayadi, M., & Seyed Ameri, M. (2018). Assessing the need of Urmia citizens for public sports. *Applied Research in Sports Management*, 4(14), 63-74.
10. Hosseini, S. M., Aghaei, N., Elahi, A., & Saffari, M. (2017). Studying Tehran Municipality Behavior with regard to Public Sports by Principles of Good Urban Governance. *Scientific Journal Of Organizational Behavior Management in Sport Studies*, 4(4), 21-36.
11. Hosseini, T., Heidari Nejad, S., & Azmasha T. (2018). The role of motivation on the level of participation of the elderly in public sports. *Research in sports management and motor behavior*, 8(16), 103-111.
12. Hsu, Y.-L., Lee, C.-H., & Kreng, V. B. (2010). The application of Fuzzy Delphi Method and Fuzzy AHP in lubricant regenerative technology selection. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 37(1), 419-425.
13. Khajavi, D., & Khan Mohammadi, R. (2015). Effect of " Green Exercise" on improving the quality of sleep in elderly women without regular physical activity in Arak. *Journal of Women and Family Studies*, 3(2), 32-37.
14. Khaki, A. A., Tond Nevis, F., Mozaffari, A. A. (2005). Comparison of the views of faculty members, coaches, athletes and managers on how to develop public sports. *Motor science and sports*, 3(5), 1-22.
15. Manafi, F., Ramezani Nejad, R., Gohar Rostami, H., & Purkiani, M. (2015). The effect of infrastructural and managerial factors on the development of sports participation in Iranian public universities. *Research in Educational Sports*, 4(9), 65-90.
16. McChesney, R. W. (1989). Media made sport: A history of sports coverage in the United States. *Media, sports, and society*, 49-69.
17. Mozaffari, A., Qara, M. A. (2005). The Status of Public Sports in Iran and Its Comparison with Some Selected Countries of the World. *Motor Science and Sports*, 6(4), 89-76.
18. Nejad Sajjadi, S. A., Hamidi, M., & Arsalan, M. (2016). Identify and prioritize landscapes and strategies of Tehran Municipality Sports Organization using AHP model. *Sports Management and Development*, 5(1), 103-116.
19. Nowruzi, A., Maleki, A., Parsamehr, M., & Ghasemi, H. (2018). Investigating the relationship between socio-economic status and the type and amount of sports participation (Case study: women of Ilam province). *Social Development*, 13(1), 119-148
20. Ranjbari, S., Aghazadeh, A., & Chaman Goli, A. (2018). Analysis of barriers to sports poverty alleviation in Iran. *Sports Management Studies*, 10(50), 86-63.

21. Razavi, S. M. H., Niazi, B. D. (2014). Designing and formulating a strategy for the development of public sports in Mashhad using a scientific perspective. *Journal of Applied Research in Sports Management*, 3(9), 49-60.
22. Ruski, C. H., & Humphreys, W. C. (2011). Swiss sports participation in an international perspective. *European Journal for Sport and Society*, 8(1-2), 15-29.
23. Sajjadi, S. A., Razavi, S. M. H., & Dousti, M. (2018). Presenting a Pathological Model of Sport Structure in Iran. *Sport Management Studies*, 10(47), 85-108.
24. Salimi, M. (2011). Investigating Barriers to the Development of Indigenous and Local Games from Students' Perspectives. *Applied research in sports management*, 4(2), 49-61
25. Seyed Ameri, M. H., Bardi, M. A., & Ghorban, B. (2012). Explaining strategies to attract and increase citizen participation in public and recreational sports programs (Case study: Urmia). *Contemporary Research in Sports Management*, 2(4), 23-34.
26. Shahbazi, M., Shabani Moghadam, K., & Saffari, M. (2013). Public sports (necessity, obstacles and solutions). *Parliament and Strategy*, 20(76), 69-97.
27. Spaniol, M. J., & Rowland, N. J. (2019). Defining scenario. *Futures & Foresight Science*, 1(1), e3.
28. Taheri Demneh, M. (2015). Examining the future images of Iranian society in the minds of educated youth. PhD Thesis, Faculty of Management, University of Tehran.
29. Toro, H. M. (2005). Public perceptions of credibility of male and female sportscasters. Virginia Tech.
30. Webb, E. (2016). Positive youth development, sport and communities: research trends and future directions. *International Journal of Sport Psychology*, 47(2), 165-186.